

BOXING UP YOUTH KNOWLEDGE AND OPINIONS ON SUSTAINABLE PACKAGING IN SERBIA

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Abstract: *Packaging is a mandatory aspect of a vast majority of produced and marketed items, thus the global packaging market is expected to grow to \$980.4 billion by 2022. Pushing the Agenda 2030 ratified by 195 nations in 2015, packaging sustainability folds under three The Sustainable Development Goals such as Responsible Consumption and Production (SDG No.12), Life Below Water (SDG No.14) and Life on Land (SDG No.15) Serbia, as one of those countries, has invested efforts in raising public awareness of sustainability issues.*

This paper is based on authors' recent survey on consumer behavior and knowledge of Serbian youth on sustainable packaging. The aim of research is to review and analyze the condition in Serbia, not only from a consumerism aspect but also from a point of view of future young professionals since all of responders are pupils or students of areas that lean toward packaging such as graphic and industrial design, also students of printing technologies. This survey refers to the level of formal design education, the level of satisfaction with the environment, level of knowledge and opinions on sustainability in Serbia. For this purpose, a questionnaire was created and contains three sections that include 17 questions related to data on demography, type and level of education, area of study; self-estimated knowledge and opinions on sustainable packaging etc. The data obtained on the sample of 321 were processed in the SPSS software package, using appropriate statistical tools. The research strategy is based on a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods. In order to review the obtained research results, descriptive statistics is applied, while the Likert scale was used to assess the satisfaction of the

respondents. Analysis of variance was used to examine differences in opinions among different groups of respondents. The questionnaire compiled to include all the necessary information on the state knowledge on sustainable packaging in order to create a comprehensive overview which is of great importance for planning further development and improvement as well as directions of further packaging and design education.

Keywords: packaging design, ANOVA, sustainability

1 INTRODUCTION

In Serbia, education in the field of packaging design has been successfully implemented for decades at both the secondary and higher education levels. The education of designers who design packaging is based on the unity of technological, ergonomic and aesthetic factors. For decades, young designers have been educated in this field, who show exceptional results in later professional work. Pupils and students go through good educational programs that develop in them a sense of visual observations, develop the ability to analyze the elements of artistic expression, a sense of surface and plastic design. Although the courses in these study programs are very extensive and meaningful, it has been noticed that no greater focus has been placed on sustainable packaging, which has become extremely important in recent years.

The concepts of packaging sustainability have evolved in parallel with the growing connection with the principles of sustainable development at different levels. Today, packaging-related waste is plagued by declining air, soil and water quality, climate change and other contemporary challenges (Boz et al., 2020). Researches in recent years have shown that young millennial consumers have developed habits in relation to the routine of packaging disposal (Nikki et al, 2019). Companies and policy makers listen carefully to these trends and respond relatively promptly to increased consumer demand for sustainability actions based on achieving the necessary common value. Today, the goals of sustainable packaging have been announced by various companies within the Sustainable Packaging Coalition (SPC) - the SPC's Goals Database (<https://sustainablepackaging.org/goals>). Various corporations, including McDonald's, Unilever, Nestle, Kraft-Heinz, PepsiCo and Coca-Cola, have set goals in their action plans to improve the sustainability of their packaging by 2025. This includes increased recycling and recycled material with a reduction in raw materials (Boz et al., 2020).

Such trends are also observed in the Serbian economy, but also among young people. What interested the authors of this research was how much young people in Serbia who are learning about packaging are actually aware of the concept and importance of sustainable packaging. The aim of research is to review and analyze the condition in Serbia, not only from a consumerism aspect but also from a point of view of future young professionals since all of responders are pupils or students of areas that lean toward packaging such as graphic and industrial design, also students of printing technologies. This survey refers to the level of formal design education, the level of satisfaction with the environment, level of knowledge and opinions on sustainability in Serbia.

2 METHODS

2.1 Sample

The rise of waste around the world became a global problem, especially in the last couple of decades. As Serbia geographically belongs to Europe, one of the most developed parts of the world, and, economically, it is not in that group, it was interesting to examine the level of awareness of Serbian youth about sustainable packaging. Since young people from Belgrade and Novi Sad make the largest part of the targeted youth population of Serbia, high school pupils and students from these two cities were surveyed. In order to achieve the goal, high school pupils from the graphic and design high school were interviewed (in terms of online surveys – School of Design - graphic, packaging and industrial design and Graphic technology High School), as well as students from the Faculty of Applied Arts Belgrade (Graphic and Industrial Design), Faculty of Technical Sciences Novi Sad (Department of Graphic Engineering and Design), and students from The Academy of Applied Technical Studies Belgrade (Department of Technology-modules Digital graphics and Graphic engineering and the Department of Design-Study programs: Industrial design and Graphic design).

The first aim of the research was to review and analyze the condition of sustainable packaging methodology in Serbia, and to analyze the consumerism aspect from a point of view of future young professionals. Therefore, pupils and students of areas that lean toward packaging were targeted as respondents for this survey. Research methodology consisted from a questioner, constructed in 3 parts with 17 questions, where the questions are constructed considering criteria of sustainable packaging for consumers in a way of making the scientific data more comparable to the consumer perception (Brovensiepen et al., 2018).

For the literature review, key words 'packaging design' and 'sustainability' are used and combined with words such as 'perception', 'behavior', 'response', 'knowledge'. Using different scientific databases, authors obtained a general overview of the topic. The papers containing a survey in eco design and/or packaging are found (Bozet al., 2020; Brovensiepen et al., 2019; Clark et al., 2019; Haoet al.,2019; Monteiro et al., 2019; Otto et al., 2021). These papers served as a base for constructing the survey that will explore the state of eco-design and packaging in Serbia, from the sustainability point view.

2. 2 Analysis of results

In the period of April and May 2021, the authors conducted a survey in order to get reliable answers on attitudes and intentions towards sustainable packaging decisions. A questioner is conducted in Google form, covering topics on demography of the respondents, their knowledge on the state of sustainable packaging and opinions on the impact of sustainable packaging on price and sales. A goal was to get answers of the representative part of the target youth population that will use or implement sustainable packaging and design in their future career. Answers of 321 respondents are obtained. The authors used pre-given answers for easier statistical processing and analysis. Five questions within the questionnaire have pre-given answers (using 5-point Likert scale) that refer to the level of agreement / disagreement or satisfaction / dissatisfaction of the respondents. The data were processed in SPSS software package, using appropriate statistical tools. In order to review the obtained research results, descriptive statistics and crosstabulation is applied and the analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to examine differences in opinions among different groups of respondents.

Figure 1: Demographics

The demographic characterization of the sample divided the answers by age in five age-classes: "18- 24"(71%), "under 18" (19%), "25-34"(6%), while the

smallest part of the sample (4%) consists of people older than 35 years ("35-44" and "over 45"), with at least 5 years of working experience. This was expected because the goal was to get opinions from young people, having in mind that people over 35 years may be students, and that's why they participate in the sample. Next characterization (by sex) indicates that more than two-thirds of respondents are female (70.72%) and nearly one third of them (28.97%) are male, while one respondent didn't give answer to a question of sex (0.31%). Next distribution is made by respondent's level of education, in terms of the current level of education that the observed respondent acquires or the highest level of education he/she has acquired so far to monitor any differences in opinions and attitudes towards this division. In this case, the distribution was the following: 45.77% of the sample are high school pupils (HS), 45.14% are students of bachelor studies (HEB), 1.57% are students of specialist studies (HESS), 6.58% are master degree students (HEMS) and 0.94% are doctoral students (PhD). As it is expected, students of bachelor studies and high school pupils make the majority of the sample (91%) and they are almost equally represented (about 45%). In order to monitor changes in opinions in relation to the field in which the respondents are engaged, the last demographic distribution of the sample was made by the area of expertise: one half of the respondents are in the field of graphic design (51.09%), just under one-third (26.79%) are from industrial and/or product design, while about 20% are from the field of graphic technology. This is understandable in relation to the fact that the field of graphic design is currently the one that has the most applications and jobs.

Climate change, population growth and rising levels of pollution have significantly burdened and threatened our planet and resources. In response to that, more sustainable solutions are required from all areas of business. In this context, it is interesting to find out the opinion of young people in Serbia about how much it is necessary to work on raising environmental awareness in their country. Thus, based on the sample, the average answer was 4.07, which means (by Likert scale), that the respondents think that is very needed to work on raising environmental awareness in Serbia ($SD=0.964$). The authors wanted to explore is this opinion more or less the same to all age-classes or it is different within groups. So, a crosstabulation analysis is applied (Pallant, 2009) and showed that 47.8% respondents older than 25 (in age class „25-34“, „35-44“, and „over 45“) think that is very needed to work on raising environmental awareness in Serbia; while that opinion hold 34.9% respondents in age-class „18-24“ and 28.3% respondents in age-class „under 18“. Moreover, 39.3% of all respondents in age-class „18-24“ and 36.7% of all respondents under 18 years old think that is extraordinary needed to work on raising environmental awareness in Serbia. It is interesting to note that in the age-class „18-24“,

73.7% of all respondents think that is very to extraordinary needed to work on raising environmental awareness in Serbia. On the other hand, no one older than 25 years think that it is not needed to work on raising environmental awareness in Serbia, while 1.7% from 18 and 24 years and 1.7% under 18 years old have that opinion, so the conclusion is that young people in Serbia, especially ones older than 25, have the awareness of a need to raise environmental awareness and the desire to work on it. Crosstabulation for the question of need to work on raising environmental awareness in Serbia vs. education level by column showed that almost equal percent of high school respondents (one third each) think that it is average / very / extraordinary needed to raise environmental awareness in Serbia, while in group of bachelor studies, master studies and PhD respondents nearly one third think that it is very needed to raise environmental awareness. Nearly two third think that the raise is extraordinary needed. 73.8% of respondents gave general assessment 4 or 5 (very to extraordinary), while only 1.6% of respondents think that there is no need for raising environmental awareness.

To achieve a goal of getting opinions about environmental needs and awareness of a respondents, a question Q9: "Have you participated in actions of cleaning open, public spaces from packaging and other waste?" is asked. Descriptive statistics showed that one half of the respondents did not participate in actions of cleaning open, public spaces from packaging and other waste, while 45.2% participated in small local cleaning actions and only 4.4% participated in big public leaning actions.

Figure 2: Packaging Q9-Q12

Crosstabulation for the question of participation in actions of cleaning open, public spaces from packaging and other waste vs. education level by column

showed that almost two third of high school respondents, two third of PhD respondents and one third of Bachelor degree respondents didn't participate in actions of cleaning open, public spaces from packaging and other waste, while 60% of master degree and 71.4% of master degree respondents gave general assessment 4 or 5 (very to extraordinary), while only 1.6% of respondents have participated in small local cleaning actions. This means that young people need to be both informed and motivated to participate in actions of this type.

Crosstabulation for the question of participation in actions of cleaning open, public spaces from packaging and other waste vs. age by column showed that 58.36% of high school pupils, 50.7% of young people between 18 and 24 years and 44,4% of people between 25 and 34 years didn't participate in actions of cleaning open, public spaces from packaging and other waste, while the biggest percent of participants in big public cleaning actions is 12.5% of people between 35 and 44 years old. Among respondents that have participated in small local cleaning actions the biggest percent are people between 35 and 44 years (75%), while the biggest percent of people that didn't participate in any kind of cleaning actions are people under 18 years (58.3%).

Getting the answers to a question Q10: „How well do you think you know the concept of sustainable packaging? “ was next important goal. Descriptive statistics showed that the average assessment is 2.77 (SD=0.985), which means that the young in Serbia think that their knowledge of the concept of sustainable packaging is average. The authors wanted to explore is this assessment the same by all age-classes, does it differs depending on aducational level and the area of expertise. To achieve this goal, a crosstabulation is applied. So, crosstabulation of Q10 vs. age confirmed the sample average assessment. Crosstabulation by education level showed that bachelor, master and PhD students' attitude is the same as of the sample, while high school pupils opinion differs from the average. It is interesting to note that PhD students gave the highest evaluation-33% of them think they know the concept of sustainable packaging excellently. Crosstabulation of Q10 vs. area of expertise showed that 46.8% of respondents from the graphic technology area think that don't know or know a little bit about the concept of sustainable packaging. Graphic technology, graphic design and industrial/product design respondents (44.9%) think that their knowledge about the concept of sustainable packaging is average, while one respondent, who is from both graphic design and industrial/product design doesn't know anything about the sustainable packaging concept. It is interesting to note that respondents from graphic design with graphic technology are best informed about this concept, while graphic design respondents are least informed.

As a matter of ecological worry, a question “How worried are you about the pollution and the ecological situation in Serbia at the moment?” is asked. Crosstabulation vs. age showed that people between 35 and 44 are extremely worried, while the others are very to extremely worried. Crosstabulation vs. educational level showed that high educated people (subgroups of bachelor, master, specialist an PhD students) are extremely worried, while pupils are worried on average. On the other hand, a crosstabulation vs. area of expertise showed that only subgroup of industrial/product design isn’t worried, while others are very to extremely worried.

PACKAGING Q13 - Q17

Figure 3: Packaging Q13-Q17

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) compares the means of two or more independent groups in order to determine whether there is statistical evidence that the associated means are significantly different between observed groups of respondents. The authors explored are there differences in responses to the questions of sustainability concerning age-class, educational level or the area of expertise. One-way ANOVA is used when the data are divided into groups according to only one factor (Ostertagova, 2013). ANOVA is applied to questions Q11-Q17 shown on Images 2 and 3 that represent dependent variables.

Descriptive analysis of Q11 by age, educational level and area of expertise showed that the groups are very different by size. The homogeneity of variance test showed that the condition of homogeneity is fulfilled (the value of Levene's test is higher than 0.05) in all cases except: Q11 by age and area of expertise, Q12 age and education level, Q13 by education level and area of expertise and Q14 by age and education level. F-test ($F(317)= 5.304$, $\text{sig}=0.000<0.05$) showed that there are two cases with statistically significant difference between the mean values of the dependent variable among the observed subgroups: the first one is between the mean values of the dependent variable Q17 among the observed subgroups by area of expertise, where multiple

Comparisons table showed that the average assessment of respondents from the area of graphic design is statistically significant than from the respondents of graphic technology ($M=-0.483$, $\text{Sig}=0.000$); and between ones from the area of graphic technology and industrial/product design ($M=0.435$, $\text{Sig}=0.125$); the second one for Q15 by age, where F-test ($F(317)=3.835$, $\text{Sig}=0.005<0.05$), and Comparisons table showed that the average assessment of respondents from age-class „under 18“ is statistically significant (at 0.05 level) than the one from the age-class of „35-44“ ($M=-1.642$, $\text{Sig}=0.569$). On the other hand, robust test of Equality of means is applied for the cases where the homogeneity is not fulfilled and indicated that the existence of statistically significant differences between the mean values of the dependent variable Q13 among the observed subgroups by educational level, Q14 by age and Q15 by should be examined. Subsequent analysis (Dunnett's test) showed the existence of only one statistically significant difference between the mean values of the dependent variable Q13 among the observed subgroups „under 18“ that have lower mean value than the age-class of „over 44“ (Mean Difference= -1.767 , $\text{Sig.}=0.009$).

3 CONCLUSION

The authors' recent survey on consumer behavior and knowledge of Serbian youth on sustainable packaging is based on our motive to review and analyze the condition in Serbia that may lead to improvement and adjustment of our current or creation of new study programs to a more circular approach. The survey is based mostly on youth (18-35 years of age) and on students and young professionals in areas that gravitate to packaging –graphic and product design and graphic technology.

Their opinions vary depending on the topics and based on their age and education level more than on the main area of study or gender. The only exception from this is the question to evaluate their knowledge on sustainable

packaging where interviewers coming from graphic technology expressed less knowledge than their design peers. While Serbian youth is not ready to roll up the sleeves to achieve better environment since nearly half of the interviewers did not take part in any cleaning of public spaces, they do show a lot of understanding and awareness about the ecological issues. The awareness rises with age and level of education. This clearly opens the door to create the first multidisciplinary short course in sustainable design and technology in Serbian higher education system.

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